

MANUFACTURING STUDY WITH THIN-PLY COMPOSITE PREPREGS IN AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT (AFP)

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ABSTRACT

Composite aerospace structures offer high specific mechanical properties as compared to traditional materials, yet composite materials tend to lack sufficient damage tolerance. In recent years there has been a focus on thin-ply pre-preg materials, which have shown an improvement with respect to micro-cracking and fatigue resistance as compared to the standard-ply-thickness materials. Large scale automated composite manufacturing processes, such as automated fiber placement (AFP), are necessary to produce large structures reliably and affordably. However, thin-ply materials require more layers to reach the same thickness, increasing the number of passes by the AFP machine. The overall production time is thereby increased, increasing the importance to maximize lay-down rate and minimize machine downtime. Thin-ply materials have not yet seen widespread adoption in AFP manufacturing in part due to a lack of study and development that leads to uncertainty associated with their manufacture. The result is that thin-ply materials lack the same repeatability, consistency and quality as standard-ply-thickness composites in the AFP process.

In this work, efforts to identify key material and AFP processing parameters of thin-ply materials that result in high quality, consistent and repeatable feed of material through the AFP head and onto the structure are presented. A single spool, in-house designed machine is used to mimic the AFP process using a 70 gsm thin-ply material. The material-process parameters and interactions are studied using a design of experiments (DoE) approach. The factors being studied fall into three main categories: material parameters, slitting and spooling parameters, and AFP process parameters. Some of the factors being studied include out-time, backing paper vs. double-backing paper, and pre-preg tape tension. The DoE program is supplemented with finite element models (FEM) of the relevant manufacturing parameters.

1 INTRODUCTION

Automated Fiber placement has become a standard way of creating large composite aerospace structures such as fuselages and cryogenic pressure vessels, due to its benefits over traditional hand-lay-manufacturing processes. Some of the benefits of AFP are increased accuracy and repeatability, less material waste, and the ability to have complexities in the part design [1]. Though composites materials, when used with AFP, can help reduce the cost of structures, composites often lack sufficient damage tolerance [2]. Microcracks can develop as a result of impact, post-manufacture residual stresses, exposure to extreme temperature changes in space, particularly around attachment points (e.g. mechanical fasteners). Due to the need for composite laminates to withstand damage over their service life, the parts are often over-designed, which unnecessarily increases the mass of the part. Overdesigning the parts negates the potential mass savings that composite parts typically have over traditional metal parts.

Recently, thin-ply composite materials (i.e., cured ply thickness below 0.0025 inches) have emerged as a potential approach for producing high-performance, thinner, lightweight structures with

improved resistance to microcracking and fatigue relative to their standard-ply-thickness composite counterparts (i.e., cured ply thickness >0.0055 inches). Thin-ply composites structures have shown to have benefits including suspension of matrix cracking and delamination under static, dynamic, and impact loading [3-5].

Combining thin-ply composite materials with automated processes such as AFP, would enable the cost-efficient manufacture of structures such as aerial vehicles and space structures that require the increased fatigue resistance properties. However, because thin-ply materials require more layers to build up to the same laminate thickness, the greater number of passes by the AFP head increase the total production time. Because AFP equipment is a costly capital outlay, it is important to maximize lay-down rate and minimize machine downtime. Without the end-user experience and feedback, material manufacturers have not fully developed their thin-ply material systems with the same repeatability, consistency, and quality of their standard-ply-thickness composites. Thus, further process development is necessary in order to understand how the thin-ply material behaves in order to optimize thin-ply tapes for AFP. Based on this need for process development, a DoE approach will be used to investigate key parameters within the manufacturing process. A combination of physical testing and simulation will be used to down select the identified parameters to determine the ideal processing parameters for AFP manufacturing with the thin-ply tapes.

2 DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS (DOE) SELECTION

A Design of Experiments (DoE) matrix was formulated to consider all of the key variables of the overall process to manufacture a part from thin-ply material by AFP. The DoE does not consider variation of the manner and repeatability with which the prepreg itself is manufactured. The key manufacturing variables were divided into three categories: (1) environmental variables that can impact raw material properties, (2) variations in the way the material is slit and/or spooled, and (3) AFP process parameters deemed important based on prior processing experience. The combination of these parameters will ultimately affect the repeatability and quality of lay down, regardless of AFP machine system type.

Based on previous AFP manufacturing experience with thin-ply materials, ten critical parameters were identified between all three categories. For environmental parameters, the two identified were tack-life and humidity. For slitting and/or spooling, backing paper was the only critical parameter chosen. The remaining seven critical parameters identified are related to the AFP machine itself. These parameters include scoop size, compaction roller hardness, pinch roller hardness, tape angle, tape tension, compaction pressure and IR heater temperature. For each variable identified, either two or three levels were defined to keep the overall DoE matrix size manageable.

Once the critical parameters were determined and the levels for each parameter chosen, these were entered into a design of experiments software package. For this project, the software package MiniTab was used to generate the full DoE matrix. The chosen critical parameters and levels can be seen in Table I. A full factorial design was initially chosen to start as it includes all interactions between the factors. However, due to the matrix yielding a total of 5,184 experiments, initial testing instead will start with looking at each parameter individually. By observing each parameter independently, any differences in the quality of the test part between the levels can be determined. If there are no discernible differences in quality then the parameter can be considered insignificant and can be removed from the overall DoE matrix. If there are discernible differences seen between the levels of the parameter, then further testing of potential interactions with other significant parameters will be conducted.

During testing any issues such as, material build-up with in the machine components, failure with the material feed at any point within the AFP head, and adhesion failure, will be recorded for each experiment. After the test specimen lay-up is completed, it will be inspected for the presence of: gaps, overlaps, tow twisting, wrinkles, de-bonding etc.

Parameter Type	Critical Parameters	Levels
Environmental Parameters	Humidity	Low humidity (50-60%) High humidity (80%)
	Tack	Fresh 5 days 10 days
Slitting and Spooling Parameters	Backing Paper	Single backing paper Double backing paper
AFP Process Parameters	Scoop Size	0.5 length
		0.67 length
		1.0 length
	Compaction Roller Hardness	Soft rubber (35A)
		Hard rubber (80A) Steel
	Pinch Roller Hardness	Soft rubber (35A)
		Hard rubber (80A) Steel
Angle of Tape with Respect to Head	Spool directly above AFP head (0°)	
	Spool maximum distance from head (~45°)	
Tape Tension	0.44 N	
	2.0 N 3.34 N	
Compaction Pressure	Low pressure	
	High pressure	
Infrared Heater Temperature	25°C	
	38°C	

Table 1: Summary of Critical Design of Experiments Parameter

3 TESTING APPROACH

After identifying the critical parameters and defining the DoE matrix, the parameters will be down-selected based on significance, using a combination of physical testing on an in-house AFP, single-tow machine, and an Abaqus process model. Once the ideal parameters and levels are selected, full scale testing on a robotic arm style AFP will be used to further refine the ideal processing parameters. These parameters can then be used for full production manufacturing of thin-ply composite parts. For all testing, a 70 gsm IM7/8552-1 thin-ply prepreg material was used.

3.1 In-house AFP machine

The physical testing was conducted on a gantry style machine with a print bed area of one square meter, onto which an in-house designed, single-tow AFP-style head is mounted. This custom AFP machine is shown in Figure 1.

The AFP head was designed in-house and mimics the functions of a commercial AFP head. The design can be seen in Figure 2, and consists of a pair of feed rollers that pull the material down, where

a scoop guides the material around and under the compaction roller. The design also utilizes two pneumatic cylinders: one cylinder that cuts the prepreg material and one cylinder that applies the needed compaction force to the compaction roller.

Figure 1: In-house designed AFP machine.

Figure 2: CAD model of AFP head.

The in-house AFP design is capable of testing all of the ten identified critical parameters. With the use of the pneumatic sliders the AFP head is capable of a compaction force range of 14 lbf to 45 lbf, which is equivalent to 200 lbf to 250 lbf on a full scale AFP machine. With the use of a magnetic particle brake, the tension applied to the prepreg tow can be varied from 0.03 lb to 0.8 lb.

3.2 Abaqus process model

Using the commercial finite element analysis (FEA) software, Abaqus, a process simulation was developed to capture the effect of some AFP process parameters on quality of laydown of thin-ply materials. The model was set up such that a single ¼" wide tow is fed from a set of feed rollers, down to the nip region where the compaction roller presses the material against a tool surface, as seen in Figure 3. The model is capable of varying: compaction roller hardness, feed roller hardness, compaction roller pressure, tape tension, and angle of tape.

By utilizing the model to investigate these parameters, the amount of physical testing can be reduced and the interactions between parameters can be investigated. The slit tape material is modeled utilizing 2D shell elements, as shown in Figure 3, where the width and thickness of each shell element represents the width and thickness of a tow of IM7/8552-1 70 gsm slit tape. The shell elements account for in-plane shear stiffness, tensile and compressive stiffness, tow compaction, friction, and bending stiffness, which are all necessary for accurately predicting material-process interactions. Note, however, that environmental effects (e.g., temperature, out-time, humidity) are not accounted for in this material model. The goal is simply to attempt to quantify the level of criticality of many of the AFP process parameters and determine if experiments are necessary to investigate interactions with other parameters that may include material parameters such as tack-life and humidity.

As shown in Figure 4, the two feed rollers spin toward each other to drive the prepreg material downward to the compaction roller. A tie constraint has been implemented at the very beginning of the slit tape to "tack" it down to the surface and prevent it from lifting (thus compromising the ability of the simulation to execute fully). In order to avoid requiring the compaction roller, feed rollers, and slit tape to all move in unison, the model was set up such that the tool surface translates horizontally to achieve laydown. As material is being laid down, the compaction roller force can be adjusted, the initial position of the tape relative to the roller (Figure 5) can be adjusted, and the tension in the tape itself can be adjusted. The roller hardness is adjusted via applying different material cards for the rollers (i.e., metal vs. rubber).

Figure 3: AFP process simulation geometric set-up in Abaqus.

Figure 4: Loads and constraints applied to the AFP process model geometry in Abaqus.

Figure 5: Stress in material varies depending on tape approach angle (left) 90°, (center) 60°, and (right) 45°.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The key processing variables associated with the AFP manufacture of thin-ply materials are investigated to identify those (1) environmental variables that can impact raw material properties, (2) variations in the way the material is slit and/or spooled, and (3) AFP process parameters that are critical to high-quality part production. The ideal processing parameters for the IM7/8552-1 70gsm thin-ply material will be translated to an AFP set-up to verify that the small-scale experimental and computational approaches properly scale. This will allow manufacturers to reduce some of the costly process validation and certification processes for future thin-ply composite structures.

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